

LEGAL SYSTEM AND THE ROLE OF THE LEGAL SYSTEM IN LEGAL SCIENCE AND THEIR RELATIONSHIPS.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10878373>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 19th March 2024

Accepted: 24th March 2024

Published: 26th March 2024

KEYWORDS

law, legal system, national legal system, code, social relations, legal creativity, international cooperation

ABSTRACT

This article shows the concept of legal system and legal system and their characteristics, mutual relations between legal system and legal system, their place in jurisprudence, and their expression in social relations.

By the 21st century, all spheres of social life are developing rapidly all over the world. The peoples of the world are striving to improve in every sphere. In the current era, when radical reforms are being implemented in all spheres of social life, it is important to study the phenomena of state and law, understand the law and apply the law staying is one of the urgent issues. No matter how different social relations are, they are subject to certain laws, they are created on the basis of the laws of society, and therefore they exist as a specific system. The change and renewal of social relations finds its reflection and expression in the legal system and the legal system of a country is an expression of social relations in this society.

The concept of the legal system entered the legal science in the last quarter of the 20th century, and today it appears along with the political, economic, and social systems. The development of the legal system is directly related to the economic, social, and political situation in this country and is manifested in the political and legal consciousness and culture of the population.

In other words, the legal system of a particular country is the law that applies in the territory of this country and regulates social relations in society. The legal system embodies the level of legal development in the country, concepts of law, legal institutions, legal processes and all other legal realities, and represents the interdependence between them.

The concept of legal system is interpreted differently by legal scholars. Some authors understand <<legal system>> as the same as the phrase <<legally system>>, while other scholars refer to the relationship between legal norms and legal relations within this concept. Some experts state that <<the concept of legal system as a normative structure covers the structure of law, the activities of authorized bodies in the field of law creation and law enforcement>> [1]. According to Academician V.S. Nersesyans, defining the legal system, in its

essence, means the general understanding of law, conditionally replaced by the word <<legally system>>[2] .

According to Professor M. N. Marchenko's point of view, the legal system means the entire legal structure of the country, consisting of the sum of all legal institutions and institutions operating within the framework of a country, legally organized as a single entity of society [3].

According to professor N.I. Matuzov, the legally system can be defined as a set of internally coordinated, interconnected, social legal instruments [4]. In juridical science, the category "legally system" was initially seen together with concepts such as "legal system" and "legal system". Various opinions are expressed about it. Most scientists are based on a normative view of the legally system [5].

Law is a regulator of social relations. Social relations can consist of different components, but they unite to a certain extent in groups. We can observe this objective process in parallel, and such a process carried out by law is interpreted as an independent legal category on the subject of the legal system. Legally system- the internal structure of the law is the internal structure, it shows what parts the law consists of and the relationship and ratio between the parts.

To sum up, the legal system is the internal structure of law. They include the rule of law, the institution of law and the field of law. Legal documents, legal institutions and their activity as a whole organism.

Bibliography:

1. Alekseev S.S. General theory of law. T.1.-M: 1981, pp. 87-88.
2. Problems of the general theory of law and state / Responsible editor: V.S. Nersesyants. - M: 2000, P. 450.
3. Marchenko.M.N. Theory of state and law and questions and answers.-M: PBOYUP Grachev S.M, 2001.P.131.
4. Matuzov N.I. Legal system and personality. Saratov.1987.P.26.
5. Alekseev S.S. Theory of law.-M.1995.P.88-97.
6. Islamov Z.M. Society. State Law (issues of theory). - M. Adolat, 2001. P. 508.